

A Methodology for Designing Sustainable Urban Mobility Interventions Towards Climate Neutral Cities

Iason Sioutis¹, Vangelis Angelakis², Anna Antonakopoulou¹, Vasileios Sourlas¹,
Ida Grundel³, Tina-Simone Neset⁴, and Angelos Amditis¹

¹ Institute of Communication and Computer Systems, I-SENSE Group, Athens,
Greece

{iasonas.sioutis, anna.antonakopoulou, v.sourlas, a.amditis}@iccs.gr

² Linköping University, Department of Science and Technology, 60174, Norrköping,
Sweden

³ Linköping University, Department of Thematic Studies – Technology and Social
Change, 58183, Linköping, Sweden

⁴ Linköping University, Department of Thematic Studies – Environmental Change,
58183 Linköping, Sweden

{vangelis.angelakis, ida.grundel, tina.neset}@liu.se

Abstract. The paper outlines the methodology proposed in the European project ELABORATOR, aiming to support European cities in their efforts on person-centered mobility towards climate neutrality. At the centre is the UN SDG 11, which will be addressed via following a co-creation approach, adhering to the quadruple helix model and around articulating and designing urban interventions for all citizens. The employed methodologies facilitate a genuine relationship between citizens and other urban stakeholders via a meet-in-the-middle approach, seeing the city as a meeting place where all involved actors of the helix can co-create to generate new value. This is vital for ensuring societal relevance, unlocking innovative pathways, to support solutions' adoption and longevity [1]. It is a multi-stage co-creation process encompassing co-designing, co-production, and co-evaluation, spanning in four phases: 1) The Set-up phase establishes a toolkit for evaluating urban mobility indicators, setting baselines while ensuring broad citizen participation. 2) Within the Discovery and Definition phase, actors collaboratively identify local mobility gaps and prioritize interventions, introducing a twinning methodology for knowledge transfer across cities. 3) In the Implementation phase, stakeholders engage in knowledge co-production, assessing each intervention using participatory tools. ICT tools are developed for structured information collection and organization, accessed via a data marketplace, and enabling cross-evaluation. 4) The Evaluation phase follows the steps of before and after studies, where pre-intervention is compared with post-intervention.

Keywords: Urban Mobility · Sustainability · Inclusivity · Co-Creation.

1 Introduction

1.1 Urban Mobility context in Europe

The European Union is confronted with a broad spectrum of demographic, public health, and environmental challenges, which encompass climate change, road safety stagnation, increasing urbanization, ongoing violations of air quality standards in over 100 cities, a rising obesity epidemic, and the effects of an ageing population[2]. To tackle these multifaceted issues, there is a growing acknowledgment across various levels of government —from local to national and EU-wide— about the importance of promoting active mobility, particularly through walking and cycling (see e.g. [3]. This strategic shift is not only aimed at addressing the myriad challenges but is also recognized for its potential economic benefits, with estimates suggesting that cycling activities in the EU generate approximately 150 billion euros annually [4].

During the Covid-19 pandemic, the necessity for safer mobility while maintaining physical distancing accelerated the adoption of infrastructure changes to support active mobility across major European cities. These changes included the expansion or creation of new cycling lanes and the introduction of lower speed limits to facilitate safer travel and encourage the shift away from private vehicle use towards more sustainable and active transportation options, going beyond fossil-free public transport, such as walking and cycling [5].

Efforts are underway to use and update Sustainable Urban Mobility Indicators [6] to collect and analyze data on mobility patterns, particularly focusing on challenges faced by vulnerable groups. Such research is integrated with other interdisciplinary studies to design public spaces that are inclusive and meet the safety and accessibility needs of all users, including those who are vulnerable. Guidance is provided to urban areas and member states on integrating considerations for vulnerable road users into infrastructure planning, utilizing digital and smart technologies to enforce speed limits, and regulate vehicle access. This includes designing services and public spaces to be inclusive, such as mobility hubs and public transportation that should cater for a diverse population of travelers [7].

Learning from the experience of the Covid-19 pandemic adjustments, strategies are being developed to enhance the resilience, safety, and accessibility of public infrastructure to better prepare urban areas for future challenges. Additionally, the integration of lessons learned is crucial for fostering synergies and ensuring alignment with broader EU objectives [8].

1.2 The ELABORATOR project

Within this context, ELABORATOR will furnish methodologies, practical tools, recommendations, and guidelines intended to assist urban planners and industrial technology stakeholders in crafting innovative products, services, and interventions for implementation within intricate urban landscapes. Moreover, it aims

to aid authorities and policymakers in formulating political strategies geared towards integrating safe, sustainable, and inclusive urban mobility into our daily lives, thereby aligning with the objectives of the Climate Neutral and Smart Cities Mission. Additionally, ELABORATOR will expand its pre-assessment capabilities to offer local authorities insights into future options, enabling them to test and refine forthcoming policies. The reception of any novel urban mobility solutions and interventions by citizens holds significant interest for all stakeholders within the relevant sectors. Numerous studies emphasize that the success of new technologies hinges on user acceptance. This acceptance, and subsequently, the degree of adoption, not only yields commercial implications but is also pivotal in mitigating risks of social exclusion. Thus, the extent of user involvement throughout the entire process, spanning from design to evaluation and adoption of innovations, emerges as a critical factor in system sustainability. While previous research has often explored the link between the quality of mobility services and resulting social impacts (see for example [9] and [10] and the references therein), fewer studies have delved into the accessibility and applicability of both physical and digital mobility solutions across various social groups [11].

1.3 The ELABORATOR challenges

ELABORATOR envisions and endeavors to accelerate the transition towards inclusive and fair active and environmentally friendly mobility frameworks. This will be achieved through collaboratively devised activities aimed at implementing targeted urban interventions. These efforts are centered on mitigating transportation externalities such as emissions and road accidents, thereby making substantial contributions to the EU cities' goals of climate neutrality and vision zero. This involves addressing the following challenges:

Challenge 1: Lack of cohesion and fragmentation in the smart mobility sector. The transportation sector typically involves collaboration between private and public operators. However, there is often a lack of comprehensive understanding of the entire process necessary for achieving safe, inclusive, and sustainable mobility. This lack of cohesion, coupled with a deficiency in strategies to motivate citizens to adopt new habits and alleviate concerns regarding the use of new technologies, hampers the realization of an "inclusive" mobility as a societal service.

Challenge 2: Low understanding of mobility needs of citizens (particularly vulnerable to exclusion groups and Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs)) and analysis of barriers and obstacles to safe, inclusive, affordable and sustainable urban mobility. Mobility needs are influenced by four primary pillars shaping current urban environments:

1. Climate change and compromised air quality standards: The transportation sector accounts for a quarter of Europe's greenhouse gas emissions, primarily

contributing to urban air pollution. Globally, transportation-related pollution, particularly from fine particles (PM_{2.5}) and ground-level ozone, leads to approximately 11 % of the annual premature deaths. Road transport alone is responsible for 70% of transportation emissions. The EU's low-emission mobility strategy emphasizes the necessity for cities to address increasing mobility needs in a safe, sustainable, and inclusive manner.

2. **Rising urbanization, population growth, and safety challenges:** Urban population has surged by 25% since 1950, with estimates predicting a further increase to 68% by 2050. This growth intensifies the demand for mobility, prompting a proliferation of new mobility modes. However, this surge in movement, coupled with evolving technologies, complicates urban flows and safety concerns. A third of fatal road accidents occur in urban areas, disproportionately affecting vulnerable road users. EU initiatives such as the Strategic Action Plan on Road Safety aim to reduce road fatalities and serious injuries.
3. **Population aging, health, and well-being:** Mobility significantly impacts physical activity levels, community engagement, mental health, and independence, particularly for the elderly and disabled. Numerous health indicators are linked to mobility. With obesity and mental health issues affecting a considerable portion of the population, cohesive transport systems are crucial, especially in nations grappling with aging populations. The EU's Smart and Sustainable Mobility Strategy aims to reduce transport emissions and promote active transportation.
4. **The COVID-19 pandemic-induced mobility shift:** The pandemic brought about significant changes in citizen behavior and mobility patterns, driven by isolation measures and social distancing. Public transportation was notably affected, leading to a surge in bicycle and pedestrian trips. However, in cities lacking safe infrastructure for active modes, there was an increase in road accidents. The pandemic underscored the necessity for accessible, affordable, and sustainable mobility services, along with safety considerations for emerging transportation modes. Long-term changes in workplace dynamics, including increased remote work, also emerged.

Challenge 3: Need to align and synchronise technological, economic and social scopes of new urban mobility developments. Efficient planning and design of sustainable urban mobility should integrate technological advancements alongside solutions centered on societal needs. As per a 2017 Eurostat report, one out of every seven individuals faces challenges with basic activities or has a disability. The rapid digitization of mobility services can create significant obstacles for specific user groups, leading to their exclusion and isolation. Future mobility solutions should be developed through a collaborative approach that considers both social and environmental sustainability, as well as economic feasibility, in response to societal expectations and requirements. Early and close collaboration, knowledge exchange, and co-design among various stakeholders—including the private and public sectors, municipalities, industries, academia, regulators,

policymakers, and diverse user groups such as those with reduced mobility, the elderly, pregnant women, students, migrants, non-emergency healthcare users, children, unemployed individuals, residents of disadvantaged areas, and others—are essential. This collaborative effort is imperative for aligning actions and optimizing investments to deliver impactful mobility solutions that benefit society as a whole.

2 The Methodological underpinnings of ELABORATOR

The ELABORATOR departs from the assumption that innovation should be adapted and modelled in response to the citizens’ needs, requirements, and desires in cooperation with the local stakeholders’ perspectives and capabilities, depending on each city’s socioeconomic and technological context. These innovations need to be designed and developed in a co-creation process to respond to citizens’ needs rather than just providing alternative/new options in their everyday life. Another key aspect is the inclusion of perspectives for all citizens, including ‘vulnerable to exclusion’ groups. In fact, the aspect of inclusion, equity and accessibility must go beyond simple analyses that consider age, gender, and forms of disability. The ELABORATOR ambition is to overcome current difficulties in including needs and requirements of all segments of the population in the design process of future and technologically advanced mobility products, services and urban interventions towards zero-emission, as well as shared, active and human-centred mobility. The significance of citizen participation, co-creation, acceptance and adoption in urban developments, needs to be complemented with mature and established collaboration and knowledge sharing between the EU cities with diverse characteristics, regional development and technical maturity such as the New European Bauhaus that constitutes an example of dialogue between different actors and the new EU mission (including the 100 climate-neutral cities by 2030) which is also an innovation initiative that can harness city transition. This will increase the speed of the take-up and up-scaling of innovative, best practice and replicable safe, affordable and sustainable urban mobility solutions on a European level instead of isolated pioneering or advanced or underdeveloped urban contexts that undermine and slow down the fulfilment of the EU Zero Pollution Action.

At the centre of the ELABORATOR project is UN Sustainable Development Goal 11 (SDG-11): “To make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable”. SDG-11, focusing on cities and communities, has put inclusive urban planning in the spotlight, strongly promoting participation of diverse voices in decision-making processes, particularly those of marginalized or vulnerable groups. Emphasis has been placed on safety and resilience, while ensuring equitable access to essential services and infrastructure.

The ELABORATOR focuses on vulnerable citizens in the context of urban mobility and the decision making processes around it. For the former, we typically consider vulnerable street users as individuals who face significant barriers due to physical, social, economic, or cultural disadvantages. This includes, for

example, people with disabilities, the elderly, children, low-income populations, and women. These users are often more dependent on public transportation and pedestrian pathways, which makes them disproportionately affected by poor design and functionality of urban mobility systems. Their needs and challenges require special consideration in urban planning to ensure equitable access to mobility and safety.

Participatory design processes involve a range stakeholders, including citizens, in the planning, decision-making and evaluation stages to ensure that the resulting urban mobility solutions are well-aligned with the needs of the broader community. By engaging a diverse range of voices, participatory design aims to develop transportation infrastructures such as roads, bike lanes, and public transit that are more accessible and beneficial to the broadest spectrum of citizens.

However, despite intentions for inclusivity based on participatory design, vulnerable citizens are often still at risk of exclusion. Barriers such as lack of awareness, limited outreach, and inaccessible consultation venues can prevent these individuals from engaging and participating fully, if not at all. Furthermore, cultural and language differences, along with limited technological access or literacy, can also sideline vulnerable groups. For instance, online forums and digital surveys, common tools in participatory processes, might exclude those lacking tech-savvy skills. As a result, even well-intentioned participatory designs can end up perpetuating inequalities if they fail to actively facilitate the involvement of all community segments, especially the most vulnerable. Therefore, ELABORATOR starts from the position that to truly embrace inclusivity, urban mobility planning must incorporate targeted strategies to engage these individuals directly and ensure their needs and voices are integral to the design process.

ELABORATOR builds on co-creation methodology to ensure that the perspectives of all involved stakeholders of the quadruple helix are addressed/included. Principles of co-creation are included in the definition, implementation and evaluation of the interventions. Co-creation ensures societal relevance and helps identify novel perspectives and innovative pathways, which in turn supports local uptake of solutions, and their long-term sustainability. We refer to co-creation as the overarching concept, distinguishing between consecutive process stages from co-designing to co-evaluation. ELABORATOR aims to foster a genuine relationship between citizens and other stakeholders via a meet-in-the-middle co-creation approach.

Meet-in-the-middle implies looking at the city as a meeting place where the public sector, private interest, and citizens come together to generate new value, to collaborate, and innovate together. Interventions can only be successful if they are brought about by local innovation platforms, that bring together all involved actors of the helix. This approach is preferred to both ‘top-down’ interventions informed by limited citizen participation, which carries the danger of irrelevance and limited uptake; and to ‘bottom-up-only’ approaches, which tend to lack long-term vision as well as resources to implement and see through solutions in their entire life-cycle.

3 The ELABORATOR at a glance

The principles laid out in the preceding section resonate throughout the project. They are put into practice in six “Lighthouse” cities and six “Follower” cities, who will employ citizen-centric and data-driven approaches developed within the ELABORATOR towards designing, deploying, and evaluating interventions for all citizens, with a particular focus on the needs of those who are vulnerable.

The Lighthouse cities are: Issy (France), Zaragoza (Spain), Helsinki (Finland), Milano (Italy), Trikala (Greece) and Copenhagen (Denmark). The Follower cities are Ioannina (Greece), Krusevac (Serbia), Lund (Sweden), Liberec (Czech), Split (Croatia) and Velejne (Slovenia). Connecting the Lighthouse and Follower cities will come from active networking opportunities and a range of capacity building activities involving training, knowledge and skills development, coaching, and support. The new knowledge created throughout the project will be disseminated via a knowledge hub, a shared data platform, where lessons learnt and guidance documents, as well as scientific papers will be accessible under FAIR principles, while planned events will provide other cities the potential to adapt and reuse project approaches, tools and eventually interventions in their own environment.

Fig. 1. The ELABORATOR concept has SDG 11 at the center of a meet-in-the-middle approach to co-creation of interventions and their twinning across the project Lighthouse and Follower cities.

4 The ELABORATOR Methodology

The project is broken down in four phases, namely: Setup, Discovery & Definition, Implementation, and Evaluation & Dissemination. The overall scheme of the workflow follows a design process derived from the double diamond, where we consider each diamond to be an agile cycle, and the second one having an embedded twinning cycle.

Fig. 2. The four ELABORATOR project phases and their respective activities in three cycles (Co-Design, Twinning, and Co-Production/Co-Evaluation).

4.1 The Setup Phase

In the Setup phase, the project establishes a set of methodologies and co-creation tools with the aim to identify relevant mobility indicators for the co-evaluation and to establish baselines for the evaluation of the intervention areas while ensuring a broad representation of different citizen groups in the co-creation process at each of the LLs. This approach specifically addresses vulnerable to exclusion groups in urban settings by providing an inclusion plan to be followed throughout the duration of the project. Advanced tools for active participation are evaluated and a selection is made in the form of a playbook. Furthermore, sensing kits and mobile apps are developed to enable citizen science and allow for layman evaluation of mobility indicators.

4.2 The Discovery & Definition Phase

In the Discovery and Definition phase, citizens, stakeholders, and consortium researchers jointly identify local need gaps and prioritize interventions while defining the multi-stakeholder governance of the LLs towards uptake across the project LLs. This commences by performing an investigation of current practices and policies around sustainable transportation for urban environments via qualitative and quantitative data gathering and analysis. The aim is to explore the specific challenges associated with the provision of safe, sustainable and inclusive

urban transportation and identify specific requirements of relevant actors (e.g., but not limited to local authorities, transport providers & users). Stakeholders and citizens are to be engaged in participatory workshops, aiming to identify priorities for urban mobility, as well as specific interventions already planned or running and leverage local and contextual knowledge.

The same stakeholders from both Lighthouse and Follower cities engage jointly in an Interventions' Definition set of workshops aiming to deliver the specifications of each one of the urban mobility ELABORATOR interventions, through a "Community of Practice" distributed across the relevant LLs across Lighthouses and Followers, to ensure relevance and portability. These specifications will take into account the CEAP , with each intervention following the sustainable product policy framework, in terms of design, empowered users, and circularity in production, opting for use of green, digital technologies. To this end, the project will formulate interventions via an on-demand mobility lab with "all" users and relevant stakeholders in each of the 12 LLs.

Parallel to these activities, the necessary ICT tools are developed to collect information structured and organized: All findings of the Discovery and Definition tasks will be analysed and stored in the ELABORATOR data platform. Semantic structures (taxonomies) will be utilized to model the mobility for different users'/stakeholders' types and cities' contexts and will become available via the secure, trusted and privacy-preserving data marketplace towards enabling cross-evaluation, while prediction models will be enhanced with machine learning capabilities. Additionally, via the data visualization tool, specific user-centric information will be provided to the requesters according to their interests and city contexts thus facilitating twinning, replication and uptake between the cities within the next phase of the project.

4.3 The Implementation and Evaluation Phases

In the Implementation and Evaluation phases of the ELABORATOR comprise two cycles running in parallel: the Co-Production/Co-Evaluation, and the Twinning. The former will finalise and implement specific interventions within each LL in each of the 12 Lighthouse and Follower cities and provide the quantitative evidence and user validation of the solutions employed, while the latter is the one conducting the transfer of knowledge, experiences and best practises across Lighthouses and Followers.

The Co-Production/Co-Evaluation Cycle – The LLs will vary in scale and technology readiness and will incorporate a range of technological trends and tools defined in the previous phase. Citizens and stakeholders will engage and participate in a "Solutions Co-Production" process, assessing the potential of each intervention deployed in its specific urban context, by drawing upon the participatory methodologies and evaluation tools developed in the Setup phase [12]. Solutions and interventions will be tested and demonstrated initially at the Lighthouse cities, and local knowledge produced, will allow to close the

Definition cycle for the Lighthouses through validation with groups of users and stakeholders. Meanwhile, through the twinning process, following an agile cycle described below, these definitions and the expectations of the performance of the interventions will be subject to evaluation and adaptation after a first round of testing, each at their relevant context in their respective Lighthouse cities, by the Community of Practice to ensure the effective and fast twinning.

The project consortium, by using the methodologies to extract information from the activities performed within the groups of stakeholders, citizens and real demonstration data collected will finally produce a Knowledge hub for the Community of Practice between Lighthouse, Followers and beyond. Finally, simulation tools will feed the next phase and support estimating the impact of their broader deployment to support planning and decision-making required for the rapid uptake, replication and scaling of the interventions across European cities. The lessons learnt that will be defined are related to: the long-term period, the capacity to communicate with future citizens and stakeholders and the larger-scale urban developments for inclusive, safe and sustainable mobility towards climate neutral cities.

The Twinning Cycle – The ELABORATOR Twinning methodology is collaboratively developed among project partners, and with feedback from stakeholders in the partner cities. The methodology consists of multiple building blocks, including a set of tools and methods, as well as a Community of Practice, aiming to facilitate the sharing and co-creation of knowledge and experiences across the diverse European Lighthouse and Follower Cities. The twinning methodology explores agile pathways to identify joint challenges and align the design, implementation and evaluation of specific mobility interventions in different geographical, socio-economic and cultural settings. Based on the definition of challenges and interventions, the twinning methodology enables Lighthouse and Follower cities to identify elements or complete intervention designs and explore how these can be rescaled and adapted in the Follower city’s context. While these processes are guided by a set of twinning protocols to ensure the alignment and documentation of processes, challenges and solutions, the project establishes a Community of Practice to ensure the continuous dialog and capacity building between stakeholders, experts, and practitioners from all partner cities. The Community of Practice builds on regular dialogues, knowledge exchange, demonstrations, and workshops to define and implement the interventions, and ensure their evaluation and feasibility.

5 Conclusion

The paper described the ELABORATOR methodology in supporting 12 European cities making interventions towards more sustainable, inclusive, safe, and affordable urban mobility. The approach integrates multi-stage co-creation—co-designing, co-producing, and co-evaluating across four phases: 1) A Set-up phase,

to develop tools and guides to assess needs and establish the baselines and evaluation methods at each of the 12 cities, promoting inclusivity with a focus on the vulnerable citizens. 2) A Discovery and Definition phase where the urban stakeholders identify the mobility needs and prioritize interventions, 3) An Implementation phase involves participatory assessment of interventions and the development of ICT tools for data organization, available through a data marketplace employed for sharing knowledge between cities and supporting the twinning of solutions. 4) An Evaluation phase to conduct comparative studies pre- and post-intervention to assess the effectiveness and impact of solutions deployed.

Acknowledgements The authors express their gratitude and thanks to all the ELABORATOR project members, participating cities, companies, research institutes and universities. The work in this paper has been supported by the European Union under Grant agreement ID: 101103772 of the Horizon programme (HORIZON-MISS-2022-CIT-01-01, 9/2022).

References

1. Harrison, K., Börütecene A., Löwgren J., Enlund D., Ringdahl D., and Angelakis V: Sustainability Means Inclusivity: Engaging Citizens in Early-Stage Smart City Development. *IEEE Technology and Society Magazine* **40**(3), 60–65 (2021)
2. Carmichael L., et al: Environment and health for European cities in the 21st century,” World Health Organization. Regional Office for Europe, (2017).
3. –, “Active mobility: walking and cycling”, European Commission, Directorate-General for Mobility and Transport, Available online, https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/urban-transport/active-mobility-walking-and-cycling_en. Last accessed 9 May 2024.
4. Blondiau T., van zebroec, B., Haubold H: Economic Benefits of Increased Cycling. *Transportation Research Procedia* **14**:2306-2313, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2016.05.247>, (2016)
5. Nurse A., Dunning, R: Is COVID-19 a turning point for active travel in cities? *Cities & Health*, **5**(1), (2021)
6. SUMI – Sustainable Urban Mobility Indicators, CIVITAS, Available online, <https://civitas.eu/tool-inventory/sumi-sustainable-urban-mobility-indicators>. Last Accessed 9 May 2024.
7. Soriano A, Gaikwad S, Stratton-Short S, Morgan G. Guidelines for developing inclusive transport infrastructure. UNOPS, Copenhagen, Denmark. (2023)
8. Goniewicz K, et al. The European Union’s post-pandemic strategies for public health, economic recovery, and social resilience. *Global Transitions* **1**(5) 201–209. (2023)
9. Storme, T., et al. Impact Assessments of New Mobility Services: A Critical Review. *Sustainability* **13**, 3074, <https://doi.org/10.3390.su13063074>. (2021)
10. Rey-Moreno M, Periañez-Cristóbal R, Calvo-Mora A. Reflections on Sustainable Urban Mobility, Mobility as a Service (MaaS) and Adoption Models. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* **20**(1). (2022)
11. Giorgi, S. et al. Improving Accessibility and Inclusiveness of Digital Mobility Solutions: A European Approach. In: Black, N.L., Neumann, W.P., Noy, I. (eds) *Proceedings of the 21st Congress of the International Ergonomics Association (IEA 2021)*. *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 220. Springer, Cham. (2021)

12. Broz J., et al. Designing an evaluation methodology for the Living Labs of the ELABORATOR project, in proc. of Smart City Symposium in Prague (SCSP), May 2024.